

Conventional and Atypical Antipsychotics: A Relative and Expository Review

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Abstract:- The orthodox group of antipsychotic drugs, used for almost more than half era to treat a wide range of psychiatric ailments are now being swapped in clinical as well as medical relates by contemporary ‘atypical-antipsychotics’, which embraces risperidone, aripiprazole, olanzapine, clozapine, ziprasidone and others. As a category, the new xenobiotics have been uplifted as being widely superior in clinical benefits, but the indication for this is quite challenging. In the present expository review, the therapeutic benefits, pharmacologic aspects, untoward effects, tolerability and process and product cost efficiency of the current agents are taken into consideration in contrast to the existing antipsychotics. Due to the stereotypically negligible differences between agents of the two eras in terms of the above mentioned clinical aspects and moreover because of the mounting concerns about possible opposing effects and chronic health penalties of some of the modern antipsychotic drugs, it is rational to ponder both older as well as newer agents for clinical usage and moreover it is also vital to notify patients about the considerable risks, benefits and costs of explicit selections of the same.

Keywords:- Atypical, antipsychotics, xenobiotics, untoward effect, tolerability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Antipsychotic agents are beneficial for handling an array of psychiatric syndromes. Their submissions comprise

the interim and short term treatment of mania, critical psychotic disorders, psychotic-depressive illnesses as well as disturbed states in dementia, delirium and long-standing management of chronic psychotic conditions which includes schizophrenia, schizoaffective ailment and delusional conditions.

The novel newer generation of antipsychotics have mostly replaced the of-age neuroleptic drugs such as thioxanthene, butyrophenone and phenothiazine in clinical exercise (Table 1) [1,2,3]. The progression of newer antipsychotic agents was roused by a revolutionary study in the year 1988 which exhibited clozapine to be loftier in effectiveness as compared to chlorpromazine in the management of schizophrenia patients who are resilient to larger doses of haloperidol and also not having any of the adversarial neurologic effects caused by the older generation typical antipsychotic agents [4]. A newer drug clozapine was reflected as “atypical” in bearing a very little risk of argumentative extra pyramidal indications. The term “atypical” has subsequently been used mostly to the novel antipsychotic agents which were brought into the market for the past couple of decades, regardless of their salient chemical, clinical and pharmacological diverseness [5]. In the current review, the neuro pharmacologic aspects, effectiveness and adversarial effects of orthodox antipsychotic agents are taken in consideration in contrast to some precise novel antipsychotics.

Sr. No.	Antipsychotic drugs	Available dosage forms.	Usual daily dose (mg/day)	Monthly cost in (US Dollar)
Conventional Antipsychotics drugs:				
1	Chlorpromazine (1953)	T/L/IM	75–400	25–50
2	Haloperidol (1966)	T/L/IM	4–12	15–35
3	Thiothixine (1968)	C	15–30	20–60
4	Flupenthixol (1983)	T/L	9–24	65–160
5	Flupenthixol decanoate (1983) ^{\$\$}	IM	9–24	40–80
“Atypical” Antipsychotic drugs:				
1	Clozapine (1991)	T	300–450	310–470
2	Olanzapine (1996)	T/W/IM	10–20	265–515
3	Quetiapine (1998)	T	300–600	145–275
4	Risperidone (1993)	T/L	2–6	100–250
5	Ziprasidone	T/IM	80–160	—

Table 1: Different Antipsychotic drugs with their routes of administration, dosage forms, daily dose and monthly cost

Note: \$\$= Flupenthixol decanoate is usually administered in every two week in the form of Intramuscular depot; T= Tablet; C= Capsule; IM= Intramuscular; L= Liquid oral, W= Raid dissolving wafer.

II. NEUROPHARMACOLOGY

The imposing theory and hypothesis that schizophrenia is initiated by augmented cerebral upheaval of dopamine neurotransmitter was established chiefly on the conclusion that dopamine agonists deteriorated psychosis and are clinically dynamic against psychotic and manic symptoms [6]. Hindering dopaminergic D2 receptors may be a critical or effective way to produce adequate neuro pharmacologic activity of most of the clinically potent antipsychotic drugs, particularly against delusions and hallucinations, but is not essentially the lone mechanism for producing antipsychotic action. Moreover, this act of ensuing neuro pharmaco centric assumptions about changed dopaminergic job have neither managed to accomplish a healthier understanding of the etiology of the numerous idiopathic psychotic complaints, nor have they delivered a non-empirical source for the strategy or finding of better-quality treatments for such ailments. The neuropharmaco dynamics of certain current antipsychotic agents differ significantly, with slight evidence for amalgamating hypothesis of their antipsychotic activity [7]. Orthodox antipsychotic agents, specifically those having effectiveness with high rapport and avidness for D2 binding sites (e.g., chlorpromazine and haloperidol) noticeably hinder with neurotransmission and even a very low doses, cart moderately high threats of extra pyramidal manifestations. The prominent extra pyramidal neurologic manifestations include akathisia or distressed motor restlessness, acute dyskinesia and dystonia with progressively developing parkinsonian bradykinesia [8]. The trivial jeopardy of extra pyramidal manifestations associated with “atypical “recent antipsychotic proxies (e.g., clozapine, quetiapine, ziprasidone and olanzapine) may imitate their superior affinity towards 5-HT_{2A} receptors on the contrary to D2 receptors Nevertheless, this type of receptor binding pattern is not obeyed by entire group of newer antipsychotics but is observed in certain exceptions (e.g., loxapine) [9,10].

III. EFFICACY OF CURRENT ANTIPSYCHOTICS IN CONTRAST WITHOLDER AGENTS

In a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trial conducted by *Stefan Leucht et al.* in which newer generation antipsychotic agents were paralleled with low-potency orthodox agents. As a group, the novel agents were found to be moderately more effective than less potent conventional antipsychotics. From the study conducted, it was evident that the clean benefit of newer cohort of atypical antipsychotic drugs is reduced risk of extra pyramidal side-effects (EPS) as compared with the effects associated with conservative agents. The answers might be biased by the use of certain highly potent orthodox antipsychotic such as haloperidol as a comparator in most of the trials. The probable gains in efficiency of the new age agents should be a factor in clinical practice and treatment choices to use them rather than the orthodox ones in terms of their enhanced efficacy [11].

IV. SAFETY AND TOLERABILITY OF NOVEL ANTIPSYCHOTICS

Based on the randomised controlled trials after oral administration of orthodox antipsychotic agents, atypical antipsychotics and placebo, the abrasion rate were determined. Trial statistics incriminate that a better acquiescence can be attained by preferring atypical agents over orthodox substitutes in the treatment of schizophrenia though, this effect is obvious only when the trial groups cured with the novel antipsychotic agent clozapine was selected as a drug of choice. The trial is not able to authorize for a statistically noteworthy superiority in tolerability of novel atypical agents versus orthodox antipsychotics. The rationality of the assertion that current antipsychotic drugs cater low threats of divergent effects than conservative antipsychotics is defied by results from other trials also which revealed comparable rates of treatment cessation due to adversative effects. The abundantendorsed benefit of abridged risk of extra pyramidal symptoms while using newerantipsychotics hence should be balanced alongside with the additional untoward events associated with these group of drugs [12].

V. NEUROLOGICALCOMPLICATIONS

The hazard of extra pyramidal symptoms may vary with certain antipsychotic drugs, their doses and particular neurological conditions of the patient. The advantage of the newer drugs is distinct for minimizing the threat of late parkinsonian bradykinesia and acute dystonia. No astonishingly, in pre-clinical and clinical trials, the major distinguishes in health hazard have been established by comparing modest dose of novel antipsychotic agents and high dose of immensely potent orthodox antipsychotic drugs deprived from being using them with prophylactic anticholinergic agents. When associated with less-potent first-generation antipsychotic drugs (e.g., chlorpromazine) or rational doses of highly potent drugs (e.g., haloperidol), the benefit of newer agents of abridged extra pyramidal symptoms is narrowed or eliminated as compared with the older ones [13]. Clozapine as well as quetiapine perhaps seem to be comparatively well endured by patients with Parkinson's disease those becoming psychotic with treatment progression [14]. Olanzapine and risperidone are having certain tolerance related issues. Probable dominance of novel antipsychotic agents is a little bit hazy in terms of their use in syndromes like akathisia, dyskinesias, as well as in neuroleptic malignant condition [15]. Akathisia, manifest by restlessness and anxiety, has been related with almost all antipsychotics counting clozapine. Neuroleptic malignant syndrome is a rare, hypothetically life-threatening cerebro lethal delirium, with inconstant fever, autonomic uncertainty, and muscle inflexibility including release of minglingcreatine kinase enzyme and myoglobinuria. It is significant to highlight those imperfect forms of neuroleptic malignant syndrome may happen: for instance, in patients who takes clozapine, the syndrome may be present with less noticeable muscle inelasticity [16].

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Novel antipsychotics (Table 1) cater beneficial therapeutic possibilities and the hazard of specific extra pyramidal symptoms are generally minimized with these drugs as compared to the conventional ones. As a cluster, newer antipsychotic agents differ significantly in their pharmacology and threats of certain adversative events. With an exception of clozapine, these drugs do not prove significant advantages in efficacy or tolerability over the older ones. Moreover, they are much more affluent in comparison to the orthodox group. Hence, it seems rational to think about an agent from either of group for the management of psychotic syndromes based on the relative pros and cons, jeopardies and prices related with particular selections.

Conflict of interest: The authors of the current review bears no conflict of interest.

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